

Commercial productive apple growing in a northern climate

Introduction

Northern rural areas of Europe have been featured by challenges in making a living from traditional agriculture with historically limited number of commercially cultivated species, and generally harsh climate conditions. In this context, developing new and innovative cultivation methods for growing apples that are not only suitable for northern climates but also highly productive is aimed at to diversify farms economically and environmentally. The project has planted 10 ha of apple trees, in total about 12000 apple trees, in several different plots owned by different farmers - the beneficiaries of the project in Norrbotten, Västerbotten, Västernorrland and Harjedalen regions in Sweden.

Lessons learned

To make apple production profitable the focus of any commercial operation has to be on quality and value chain rather than tonnage. The profitability for the farmers in the project comes from the connection to a high value producer of ice cider operating in a global premium market.

The project aims to develop new cultivation methods, new varieties, planting arrangements and management options to meet the demands of a new kind of buyer that in turn is ready to reward quality over quantity. It inspires farmers to go beyond business as usual and traditional agriculture in the area. Each farmer also finds their own way of managing their apple orchard - the whole idea is to learn new things for future and do observations to do things better in terms of growing apples with high sugar content suitable for ice cider production in the Northern Europe. The long-term goal of the project is to contribute to climate resilient sustainable agriculture and to create favourable partnerships between farmers and food processing companies in order to develop further products in local, regional and global markets.

The project was completed in September 2024. Overall, the project contributes to climate resilient food security, developing novel foods for consumers, economic and environmental resilience of farmers, region and local communities.

Figure 1. Apples flowering. Photo: Johan Gunséus for Brännland Iscider.

The project and its spinoffs continuously search for further collaboration with academia and other partners. If you are interested to learn more about the operational group “Commercial productive apple growing in a northern climate - innovation for new climate resilient agriculture in northern Europe”, contact Daniel Pacurar, Boreal Orchards (danielpacurar@borealorchards.se) and Andreas Sundgren Graniti, Brännland Iscider, (andreas@brannlandcider.se).

The information presented in this factsheet was developed by the FOREST4EU partner, drawing on the innovations and knowledge generated by the indicated operational group with their explicit authorization.

Further information

<https://www.brannlandcider.se/en/about-us/our-orchards/commercial-productive-apple-growing-in-a-northern-climate/>

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